

Visual identity for the project, project website and communication tools

Deliverable D7.1 v2

15/09/2022

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Author(s)	Josep Crous-Duran (REVOLVE) Patricia Carbonell (REVOLVE) Lara Barange (REVOLVE) Luciana Abbruzzese (REVOLVE)
Contact	josep@revolve.media
Reviewer	Sara Burbi (Coventry University)
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¹ R=Document, report; DEM=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; DEC=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; OTHER=other

² PU=Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CI=Classified

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1 Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.1 is about *Visual identity for the project, project website and communication tools* and was delivered in Month 6 of the project (April 2021) and reviewed in Month 23 (September 2022) after the first 18 months project review. The document is divided in three main sections containing the information related to: a) the development of the project's visual identity including logo and other graphical elements, b) the communication material developed to be used by the partner's of the project and c) the development and structure of the project's website.

A visual identity for the AGROMIX project was created to be used all throughout the project. This visual identity includes the presentation of the logo of the project as the primary visual messenger of the project, based on the "agroforestry triangle" that is a diagram used to explain the concept of agroforestry. This section also explains the slogan selected for the project ("Transforming landscapes") the typography to be used, the colour palette and the EU disclaimer including the EU finding message and the number of the grant agreement funding the project (n 862993).

Chapter 5 lists all the documents that were developed for internal sharing, use for any communication about the project and stored internally at the project's MS TEAMS channel. These documents are the Power point template, the word document deliverable template, the press release template, an informative power point project presentation, a scientific poster project template (A0 format), a project roll-up (85x200 cm) and a project leaflet (in English and Spanish).

Related to the project's website, it provides information, data and materials about the project, its partners, its pilot projects and events, and other activities organised for the project and/or by the project partners. The website was developed using WordPress and is based on a responsive web design (RWD) suitable for different browsers and screen sizes, displaying a different and optimised interface depending on the device used to access the site. Currently, the website contains six sections (1. Home, 2. About, 3. In the Field, 4. Project, 5. Newsroom, and 6. Events) and will be constantly improved and updated aiming to reach around 20.000 visits from relevant stakeholder groups, over the four years of the project's duration (2020-2024).

2 Expected impact

This Deliverable D7.1 about *Visual identity for the project, project website and communication tools* and was developed during the first 6 months of the Project as an output of Task 7.1 on *Project identity and project site* of the WP7 on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation. The main objective was to create the presentation aspect of the project and the basic communication tools to propagate the objectives of the project and put the basis to disseminate its results. It is expected that the website developed will reach an audience of at least 5.000 visitors per year for four years, reach 2.000 social media followers and help engage with at least 50 projects and/or, 8.000 stakeholders and 20.000 farmers across Europe.

3 Introduction

Deliverable D7.1 is about Visual identity for the project, project website and communication tools and was delivered in Month 6 of the project (April 2021) and reviewed in Month 23 (September 2022) after the first 18 months project review. The document is divided in three main chapters containing the information related to: Chapter 4) the development of the project's visual identity including logo and other graphical elements, Chapter 5) the communication material developed to be used by the partners of the project and Chapter) the development and structure of the project's website.

4 Visual Identity

A visual identity for the AGROMIX project was created and will be used all throughout the project. This will provide the main framework for all dissemination activities ensuring coherence and presenting a strong project image to multiple external stakeholders. across Europe. This distinctive and memorable professional visual identity for AGROMIX and associated templates, was created by REVOLVE together with the coordinator (CU) and is presented in this Deliverable 7.6 (M6) but also was [made available online](#).

4.1 Logo

The logo is the primary visual messenger of the project and is used in all the communication materials. A template pack/kit and use protocol enabled each partner to align their work with the visual identity of the project, under the guidance of REVOLVE for quality verification. This logo is represented in several color/sizes versions:

4.1.1 Main logo full color version

Main logo - full colour

4.1.2 Safe area and small versions of logos

Safe area
Keep all other graphic elements, other logos or margins at a minimum distance as defined by the "Safe area" line.

Small and tiny logos
Use the main logo until a minimum width of 20mm. Under that width please use the "Tiny" text-only version.

4.1.3 Monochrome + positive and negative small versions

4.2 Slogan

Landscapes reflect the relationship between human society and the natural environment. The AGROMIX project proposes to transform the economic, the environmental, the political, the social and technological landscapes, and that is the motivation behind the slogan: Transforming Landscapes. This slogan is used in the website and in all the dissemination materials:

4.3 Typography

The typography selected for any public communication material was : ITC Avant Garde Gothic Colours and the presentations of Headings 1, 2 and 3 were:

Ferehent antiasp elestrum qui ni id

ITC Avant Garde Gothic - Bold

Ferehent antiasp elestrum qui ni id

ITC Avant Garde Gothic - Medium

Labor modiste mquiasp eratiorerio. Nequi quam harcieni tem fugiat voloreheni coriandunt, *ut idero eum nis santi ut fuga*. Daerovi tatemore pa voluptinist, con ped earis vid quibus ut.

1234567890 #*\$€&@

ITC Avant Garde Gothic - Regular

4.4 Colours

The colour palette finally selected was:

	CMYK : C=69 M=31 Y=72 K=18 RGB : 84, 125, 86 # 547d56		
	CMYK : C=74 M=42 Y=71 K=42 RGB : 60, 87, 66 # 3c5742		
	CMYK : C=19 M=30 Y=95 K=19 RGB : 185, 151, 24 # b99718		
	CMYK : C=14 M=56 Y=94 K=7 RGB : 207, 123, 32 # cf7b20		
	CMYK : C=54 M=29 Y=62 K=12 RGB : 126, 144, 106 # 7e906a		

4.5 Graphic elements

The base graphic element is the triangle and a slanted rectangle. These elements come together to liven up a layout. The rule of thumb is to keep in mind sobriety and elegance. Usually a combination of 4 colours per page is sufficient.

4.6 EU Disclaimer

All EU funded projects' communication must display the respective disclaimer. This disclaimer was stored internally in a folder next to the project logos and other visual identity elements.

NOTE: In addition to the EU disclaimer, all the external project documents should include the following statement:

The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author's view and in no way reflect the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

4.7 Photography

The AGROMIX project has its own photo gallery for any communication purpose. More photos will be added to this archive during the project. General photos, photos from the pilot projects and event photos. The project also has a Flickr account (link): <https://www.flickr.com/people/agromixproject/>

4.8 Social Media

The social media channels created for the projects were Twitter, Instagram and LinkedIn. The specific banners, icons and images for these channels were developed and stored within the project's shared folder.

Website: www.agromixproject.eu

Twitter: @AGROMIXproject
 Instagram: @agromixproject
 LinkedIn: AGROMIX Project

Example of a banner for the project's Social Media channels.

Templates for social media shareables.

5 Communication materials

Derived from the project visual identity several documents were developed for internal sharing, use for any communication about the project and stored internally at the project's MS TEAMS channel. These documents are namely:

- Power point template
- Deliverable template. Updated September 2022.
- Press release template.
- Power point project presentation (EN)
- Scientific Poster (AO) project template
- Project roll-up (85x200 cm)
- **Project leaflet (EN, ES)**
- **EU Disclaimer logo**

6 Project Website

The AGROMIX website provides a brief, catchy and clear description of the project and its activities. It is a communication tool, promoting the project's goals and results to the AGROMIX stakeholder groups including enablers (e.g. authorities, policymakers, SMEs), leaders (industry, end-users, influential farmers) and multipliers (universities, associations, media). The website will become the primary point of contact and information for the AGROMIX community. To do so, the website will:

- Explain the project's objectives and the division of the activities by work packages and tasks,
- Present the pilot projects and trial sites,
- Provide the latest news and events related to the AGROMIX community,
- Give access to AGROMIX documents available for download such as deliverables, press releases and scientific reports,
- Act as a source of images and videos related to the project and other communication material (media kit, leaflets, posters, and newsletters),
- Offer information about the project partners,
- Direct users towards the project's social media channels (Instagram, Twitter and LinkedIn), and,
- Present the project's Knowledge Exchange Hubs as sources of agroforestry-related content organised by country.

The tone of the website content is simple, clear and straightforward, giving an overview of AGROMIX both for stakeholders and the general public. The website is designed according to the AGROMIX visual identity guidelines, making the website instantly recognisable.

6.1 Website description

The AGROMIX website provides information, data and materials about the project, its partners, its pilot projects and events, and other activities organised for the project and/or by the project partners. The website is expected to attract at least 5,000 visits per year from relevant stakeholder groups, over the four years of the project's duration (2020-2024).

The website was developed using WordPress, using a responsive web design (RWD) that is suitable for different browsers and screen sizes, displaying a different and optimised interface depending on the device used to access the site. The template is designed in a horizontal structure, integrating a menu, horizontal sliders, static banners (e.g., newsletter subscription), vertical thematic blocks, and a footer containing the required Horizon 2020 disclaimer and links for users to contact the team via e-mail or social media networks. The domain name agromixproject.eu will be maintained until five years after the project ends.

Currently, the website has six sections: 1. Home, 2. About, 3. In the Field, 4. Project, 5. Newsroom, and 6. Events. The homepage offers an overview of the project, presenting the project's most important messages in a simple, catchy and clear way, with links to other sections for further information.

6.2 Website development process

The website has been developed following a five-stage process:

1. Strategy phase
2. Wireframing phase
3. Copywriting and design phase
4. Development phase
5. Launch phase

Stage	Week 1 -2	Week 3-4	Week 5-7	Week 8-12	Week 13
Strategy					
Wireframing					
Copy & Design					
Development					
Launch					

During the strategy phase, the communications team developed a ‘Website Project Brief’ outlining the website’s objectives, timeline, approach, mood board and tone, external references, website requirements, and sitemap.

During the second stage, the communication team developed the wireframes, which are the schematic representations of the website structure. By abstracting everything visual it focuses on:

- The structure of a website
- The hierarchy of information communication
- The user journey and funnel design

Following the wireframes, every page and element must be designed, and all the content written accordingly. At the end of this phase, the partner in charge (REVOLVE) organised a meeting with the project coordinator to discuss and revise all the design and text to be included.

Once the design and the copy were approved, the communications team developed the website structure according to the wireframes, design and copy, ensuring a responsive and errorless functionality of the website for the launch phase.

The finished website was launched on 21st April 2021, and can be found at: www.agromixproject.eu. REVOLVE will regularly update the website over the project’s duration, and will take charge of its maintenance for five years after the project’s end.

6.3 Website map

6.3.1 Homepage

<https://agromixproject.eu/>

The website's homepage provides an overview of the project's main areas of work, key facts, latest features from the 'Newsroom' and 'Events' pages, and a call to action for users to subscribe to the newsletter and follow the project's social media channels. The homepage displays a menu to explore all webpages, and a search bar to find keywords across the site.

Figure 1: Project tagline and link to the 'About' page.

- The section starts with an introductory text summarising the project's background and objectives: *"Agriculture and land use are at a crossroads: Conventional agriculture is a leading cause of climate change, land degradation and biodiversity loss. However, regenerative practices such as mixed farming and agroforestry offer opportunities for agriculture to be part of the solution to these challenges. To lead this change, AGROMIX brings together farmers, researchers and policymakers to explore solutions and develop tools for more resilient land use in Europe"*.

Following the introductory text, the 'About' section displays a series of icons showing the project's various areas of action (Figure 1)

Figure 2: Main areas of work

The icons and text illustrating the project's areas of action as shown in Figure 1 are:

- Knowledge Hubs: Platform for sharing informative material and project results
- Innovative Co-design: Co-design practices applied to research and field projects
- Sustainable Business Models & Tools: Capitalisation of mixed farming and agroforestry for farmers and stakeholders across the production chain
- Immersive Learning Tools: Virtual interactive tools (serious games) that apply agroecological principles, allowing land managers to design their own agroforestry projects
- Policy Recommendations: Guidelines for decision makers to prioritise environmental resilience strategies and stable farming value chains

Following the areas of action, the section displays the latest Events and News related to the project (Figure 3)

Latest Features

Figure 3: Upcoming events and latest news

A carrousel displays key facts and figures related to the project (Figure 4). These are:

- 12 pilot projects for developing co-designed agroforestry systems
- 8 long-term trial sites for developing and testing land use models
- 12 Knowledge Exchange Hubs for sharing and storing information
- 28 partners from 14 European countries

Figure 4: Key project facts

Finally, the section contains a newsletter signup form (Figure 6), a social media feed showing the project’s latest Twitter and Instagram posts (Figure 7), and ends with a footer containing the project’s basic information, details of the coordinator, and links to the social media channels (Figure 8).

Figure 6: Newsletter form

Social Media

Figure 7: Social media feed

Figure 8: Footer displays the privacy policy, contact, and newsletter subscription form.

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6.3.2 About

<https://agromixproject.eu/about>

Both the homepage top banner and the menu link to the ‘about’ page, which describes the project and includes an illustration explaining the concepts of mixed farming and agroforestry, accompanied by an explanatory text. This page also presents quotes from each work package leader, adding a more personal tone. The page also includes the 28 partners’ logos, as well as those of MIXED and STARGATE, the two related projects that were funded under the same call.

The section starts with the text: “Coordinated by Coventry University, AGROMIX brings together researchers, farmers and policymakers to explore the transition towards resilient farming, efficient land use, and sustainable agricultural value chains in Europe”, followed by the consortium’s agreed definition of mixed farming and agroforestry, accompanied by the conceptual image of both systems (Figure 9).

Figure 9: AGROMIX conceptual graphic of mixed farming and agroforestry

Text accompanying the conceptual definition of agroforestry and mixed farming: “*Agroforestry: Agroforestry is the integration of trees with crops and/or livestock, on the same land area. This approach (if well managed) increases productivity in comparison to conventional agriculture, captures carbon, regenerates soil, and increases biodiversity. Similarly, mixed farming is the practice of integrating crop and livestock production to benefit from the resulting ecological and economic interactions.*

There are several categories of agroforestry, depending on the components (trees, crops and/or livestock), their distribution in space (linear, scattered, hedges), and their distribution in time, and they are sometimes referred to as wood pastures, intercropped and grazed orchards, grazed forests, and forest farms.

The commonality between these practices is that they allow farmers to create biodiverse landscapes that reduce their dependence on a single product, whilst positively impacting the physical environment around them”.

Figure 10: Carrousel with quotes from all work package leaders

Quotes from the work package (WP) leaders:

Ülle Püttsepp from the Estonian University of Life Sciences as leader of WP1 on Context:

“Our team is building a diversity-based resilience framework by gathering and synthesising knowledge, identifying gaps, and defining terms, which will guide AGROMIX in developing tools for resilient land use in the face of climate change.” Ülle Püttsepp (Estonian University of Life Sciences - Eesti Maaülikool, Estonia)

Daniël de Jong from Wageningen University and Research (the Netherlands) as leader of WP2 on System Design and Synergies:

“We are not changing the design, we are designing for change! To do so, we run 12 co-designed a mixed farming and agroforestry and pilot projects across Europe with a diverse group of stakeholders, leaving a legacy of meaningful impact through our co-design approach.” Daniël de Jong (Wageningen University and Research, the Netherlands)

Rodrigo Olave from the Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute (UK) as leader of WP3 on the Biophysical Indicators and Scenarios:

“Whilst mixed farming and agroforestry systems in Europe are valued for their ecological services and resources, we need to better understand how to measure resilience qualitatively, and mitigate the threat of a changing climate.” Rodrigo Olave (Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute, UK)

Alberto Mantino from the Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (Italy) as leader of WP4 on the Participatory Research and Tools for Climate-Smart Transition:

“We aim to develop a participatory approach to unlock synergies in mixed farming and agroforestry, using a holistic assessment of sustainability and resilience drivers at the farm and landscape levels, through the development of an evidence-based serious game.”

Fabio Bartolini from the University of Pisa (Italy) as leader of WP5 on the Socio-Economic, Value Chain and Network Assessment:

“We use an inclusive approach to co-create sustainable and resilient value chains for mixed farming and agroforestry. Our goal is to integrate different approaches (modelling and participatory activities) to envision future business opportunities for these land management systems.” Fabio Bartolini (University of Pisa, Italy)

Ulrich Schmutz from Coventry University (UK) as leader of WP6 on Policy Development:

“Our team researches fundamental policy challenges, co-developing policy to support national and EU institutions to overcome conflicts caused by specialisation scenarios. This work will support an ‘agroecological transition’ towards agroforestry and mixed livestock farming systems, while phasing out all industrial intensive livestock systems in Europe. Our motivation is to replace animal factory landscapes with landscapes covered with a variety of trees and free-range animals.” Ulrich Schmutz (Coventry University, UK)

Patricia Carbonell from REVOLVE (Spain) as leader of WP7 on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation:

“We use communication tools to make AGROMIX meaningful to all. Our goal is to use storytelling and visual design to evoke emotions, highlight the value of our shared natural resources, raise awareness about climate-resilient food systems, and encourage people to take action.” Patricia Carbonell (REVOLVE, Spain)

Sara Burbi from Coventry University (UK) as project coordinator:

“We understand the impact of conventional land use, and we know that we need alternatives. Mixed farming and agroforestry can build climate-resilient farming systems, but what we don’t know is how to ensure the environmental, socio-economic and policy contexts that make these solutions feasible. AGROMIX’s objective is to find answers to these uncertainties.” Sara Burbi (Coventry University, UK)

Gabriella Nagy from the CEEweb for Biodiversity (Hungary) as leader of WP9 on Ethics Requirements:

“In AGROMIX we target as many actors as possible, such as farmers, local communities, researchers, universities, policymakers, leaders of the European macro-regions, and the European Commission, sharing our message: Changes must be made now, by all of us, without boundaries, in equality for every citizen on the continent.” Gabriella Nagy (CEEweb for Biodiversity, Hungary)

Our Partnership

Figure 11: The 28 partner’s logos

Figure 12: AGROMIX ‘sister’ projects

6.3.3 In The Field

<https://agromixproject.eu/in-the-field/>

AGROMIX’s research comes from on-the-ground experience working with farmers on 12 pilot projects, and eight long-term trial sites (Figure 12).

Figure 13: Buttons directing to the Pilot Projects and Trial Sites sub-sections.

The Pilot Projects subsection is introduced by the following text: *“AGROMIX has established 12 in-depth pilot projects across Europe, which develop and test current mixed farming and agroforestry systems through a participatory co-design process, with the ambition of increasing their environmental and socio-economic resilience. These 12 projects are located in three agro-climatic zones across Europe, use different land management systems, and have different socio-economic contexts, representing a variety of farming systems in Europe. The pilot projects will be carried out in two phases: First, the participatory design approach will be tested in the first six projects; then, the methodology will be revised, improved, and tested on the remaining six”* (Figure 14) and the description of the 12 Pilot projects divided depending on the bioclimatic zone where they are located (Continental, Atlantic or Mediterranean).

Figure 14: The pilot projects are divided by their three three agro-climatic zones.

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a) Continental**Stadtbauernhof Saarbrücken**

Country: Germany

Components: Trees-crops-livestock

Farming system: Organic

Scale: Individual farm (1.8 ha)

Partner in charge: Hochschule Trier (IfaS)

Winthagen

Country: The Netherlands

Components: Crops-livestock-trees

Scale: 500 ha

Partner in charge: Wageningen University and Research (WR)

IG Agroforst Network

Country: Switzerland

Components: Trees-crops

Farming system: Conventional/organic combination

Scale: Individual farm

Partner in charge: Eidgenössisches Departement für Wirtschaft, Bildung und Forschung (AGROSCOPE)

Oikos Farm

Country: Poland

Components: Trees-grassland-animals

Farming system: Organic

Scale: Individual farm (200 ha)

Partner in charge: Ogólnopolskie Stowarzyszenie Agroleśnictwa (OSA) – Polish Agroforestry

Association of Rudno Households

Country: Serbia

Components: Trees-crops-livestock

Farming system: Conventional

Scale: 12 private farms

Partner in charge: Mreža za ruralni razvoj Srbije (NRDS)

b) Atlantic**PHAE**

Country: Belgium

Components: Trees-crops
Farming system: Organic
Scale: Farm cooperative
Partner: Instituut voor Landbouw - en Visserijonderzoek (EVILVO)

Carl Sheard's farm

Country: France
Components: Trees-crops-livestock
Farming system: Organic
Scale: Individual farm
Partner: Assoc. de Coordination Technique Agricole (ACTA)

Marston Vale

Country: United Kingdom
Components: Trees-crops
Farming system: Conventional/organic combination
Scale: Landscape
Partner: Cranfield University (CRAN)

c) Mediterranean**Co-op Manciano, Dairy Pecorino Cheese**

Country: Italy
Components: Trees-crops-livestock
Farming system: Conventional
Scale: Value Chain
Partners: Università di Pisa (UNIFI), Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (SSSA)

Tamiso Cooperative

Country: Italy
Components: Trees-crops
Farming system: Organic
Scale: Cooperative network
Partner: Veneto Agricoltura – Agenzia Veneta per il Settore Primario (VENAG)

Dehesa Farms Network

Country: Spain
Components: Trees-livestock
Farming system: Conventional/organic combination
Scale: Individual farm
Partner: Universidad de Extremadura (UEX)

Curralões

Country: Portugal
 Components: Trees-crops-livestock
 Farming system: Conventional/organic combination
 Scale: Individual farm
 Partner: Moinhos de Vento - Agroecology Research Center (MVarc)

Related to Trial Sites, the AGROMIX project works with eight well-established long-term mixed farming and agroforestry trial sites, measuring their agroecosystem’s resilience. On these sites, microclimate effects will be tested, and productivity and biodiversity indicators will be implemented, using the results to design future climate scenarios using biophysical models. Figure 15 shows how the information related to each trial site is shown. The information provided for each trial site is the following:

Figure 15: Trial sites display

Dok

Location: Therwil, Switzerland
 Establishment: 1978
 Size: 1.3 ha
 Crops: maize, wheat, clover-grass pasture, soy, potatoes
 Trees: -
 Livestock: -

Partner: Eidgenössisches Departement für Wirtschaft, Bildung und Forschung (AGROSCOPE)
Contact: Jochen Mayer, Klaus Jarosch

Dehesa of Majadas

Location: Majadas de Tiétar, Spain
Establishment: 2014
Size: 800 ha, 200 ha monitored
Crops: pasture
Trees: holm oak
Livestock: cattle, sheep
Partner: Universidad de Extremadura (UEX)
Contact: Gerardo Moreno

Arnino

Location: Pisa, Italy
Establishment: 2018
Size: 40 ha
Crops: durum wheat, sorghum, faba bean, 4-yr mixture of Italian ryegrass, orchard-grass
Trees: poplars, oaks
Livestock: dairy sheep
Partner: University of Pisa (UNIPi)
Contact: Daniele Antichi

Tenuta di Paganico

Location: Pisa, Italy
Establishment: 2014
Size: 1100 ha forest, 100 ha grazeland, 300 ha crops, 800 olive trees, 3 ha vineyards
Crops: wheat, alfalfa, faba bean, oats, mixed pasture
Trees: Turkish oak
Livestock: maremmana steers
Partners: University of Pisa (UNIPi), Tenuta di Paganico (TDPA)
Contact: Marcello Mele, Alice Cappucci, Jacopo Goracci

Lamartine

Location: Saint-Genès-Champanelle, Clermont-Ferrand, France
Establishment: 2015
Size: 4 ha
Crops: -
Trees: cherry, maple, ash
Livestock: sheep
Partner: INRAE

Contact: Mickael Bernard, Robin Russias

Loughgall

Location: Loughgall, United Kingdom

Establishment: 1989 (silvopastoral), 1999 (silvoarable)

Size: 5 ha

Crops: barley, grass

Trees: cherry, maple, ash

Livestock: sheep

Partner: Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute (AFBI)

Contact: Rodrigo Olave

Wakelyns

Location: Fressingfield, Suffolk, UK

Establishment: 1994

Size: 2.5 ha

Crops: wheat, beans, lentils, other

Trees: willow, walnut, timber trees

Livestock: none

Partner: Organic Research Centre (ORC)

Contact: Will Simonson

Restinclières

Location: Restinclières, France

Establishment: 1995

Size: 50 ha: 25 ha annual crops, 7 ha vineyards, smaller plots

Crops: durum wheat, winter pea, barley, wine, apple, alfalfa, fescue, short rotation coppice

Trees: hybrid walnut, service tree, stone pine

Livestock: -

Partner: INRAE

Contact: Christian Dupraz, Lydie Dufour

6.3.4 Project

<https://agromixproject.eu/project/#ambitions>

The 'Project' page displays the project ambitions: Increase Agroforestry Knowledge, Create new business models, Integrate agroecology in Policy, and Empower farmers & land managers (Figure 16); objectives (Figure 17); work package titles and descriptions, as well as their corresponding deliverables.

Figure 16: the project’s four ambitions

Figure 17: Banner displaying objective 1. REVOLVE created six banners associated to each of the project's objectives.

The objectives of the project and definitions are:

- **1) Increase understanding of how mixed farming and agroforestry systems work**

The project collects information from previous projects, ongoing trial sites and the experiences of farmers and land managers to identify the best options for transitioning towards these alternative land use systems in each region of Europe.

- **2) Ensure access to more sustainable produce for consumers and stable income for land managers**

AGROMIX analyses current agricultural value chains and identifies obstacles to innovation in different agro-climatic and socio-economic contexts, using these findings to present practical solutions to transition towards alternative land use systems. Implementing mixed farming and agroforestry allows farmers to diversify their production, reducing their dependence on the success of a single product, thus improving their income stability.

- **3) Create tools that support farmers and land managers in transitioning towards agroecological systems**

From its network of 83 agricultural study sites, AGROMIX has selected 12 pilot projects within three agro-climatic zones (Atlantic, Continental, Mediterranean) to develop, test and improve models and user-friendly tools to assist land managers in implementing and monitoring climate-resilient land use based on mixed farming and agroforestry principles

- **4) Estimate systems' performance across different regions**

Results from 12 in-depth studies from three agro-climatic zones (Atlantic, Continental, Mediterranean) will be used to develop models and transition scenarios adapted to the climates of each region, presenting policy options for different scales and time frames.

- **5) Develop policy recommendations for a successful transition**

With the support of innovative tools (such as serious games), AGROMIX will contribute to policy development and stakeholder-led action plans to integrate agroecological principles into existing policy frameworks. These policy recommendations will support the transition towards resilient agricultural systems that mitigate climate change in different socio-economic contexts at the local, regional, national and EU levels.

- **6) Support the development of low-carbon and climate-resilient societies**

Using a transdisciplinary, multi-actor approach, AGROMIX facilitates interaction and collaboration between researchers, farmers and policymakers, working together to design and implement low-carbon and climate-resilient societies.

- AGROMIX is divided into eight work packages. In the 'How we work' section these are presented and defined. Below you can find more information on each, as well as downloadable materials from each:

WP1: Context

WP1 contextualises and characterises mixed farming and agroforestry systems. WP1's team studies existing successful land use practices and identifies knowledge gaps, evaluating these systems' resilience to the effects of climate change.

WP2: Systems design and synergies

Due to each region's unique environmental, social and economic conditions, no one model for implementing mixed farming and agroforestry can be replicated across all of Europe's landscapes. WP2 uses a participatory design approach to design tailor-made scenarios for specific contexts based on the Reflexive Interactive Design method. This WP engages with multiple initiatives across Europe to collect data, making the knowledge collected accessible for all audiences.

WP3: Biophysical indicators and scenarios

WP3 identifies and models transition scenarios. These will be used to inform policy options and potential trade-offs in climate-smart land use systems, value chains and infrastructure at different scales.

WP4: Participatory research and tools for a climate-smart transition

WP4 studies the project's 12 pilot projects from the participative design platform (WP2), the data from modelling scenarios (WP3) and the results from the socio-economic models (WP5). This information will be used to develop and test tools and applications to support decision making for land management, including a serious game: the MIX-App.

WP5: Socio-economic, value chain and network assessment

WP5 presents the obstacles and enabling factors of implementing these land use systems at the farm and value chain levels. This knowledge is used to adapt mixed farming and agroforestry models, and to identify potential socio-economic impacts and ecosystem services of these systems, including climate change mitigation potential in different scenarios.

WP6: Policy co-development

WP6 addresses the challenge of public goods from agriculture and forestry, and identifies current obstacles to implementing these systems, such as a lack of supporting policy frameworks. This work package aims to support the development of national and EU policies (post-2020 Common Agricultural Policy) to overcome trade-offs and conflicts. The WP6 team will suggest new policies at the regional, national and EU level for farmers, advisers, processors, and other stakeholders.

WP7: Communication, dissemination and exploitation

WP7 bridges the gap between science and practice. To ensure the impact of AGROMIX's activities and research, the WP7 team uses creative storytelling and design to create shared spaces for knowledge exchange between all targeted stakeholders, ensuring collaboration with other related resilience projects and networks.

WP8: Coordination

The WP8 team manages and oversees the project's partners and activities, ensuring that AGROMIX fulfils its ambitions. WP8 ensures continuous and transparent communication flow between work packages and partners, as well as interaction with the multi-actor stakeholders, policymakers, and civil society actors engaged with the project. The WP8 team ensures that AGROMIX's research is delivered effectively, in a transdisciplinary and participatory way, and encourages engagement at the national, EU and international levels.

The page also lists the deliverables, specifying the number, title, leader, and month to be delivered:

WP1 Context:

- D1.1 Handbook of resilience and working definitions (EMU, M6)
- D1.2 Report on ecosystem services and disservices from MF/AF systems for climate-smart agriculture (CU, M9)
- D1.3 Report on indicators of resilience of farming systems to climate change (WR, M9)
- D1.4 Report on the impact of climate change on mixed farming and agroforestry systems in Europe (UEX, M12)
- D1.5 Report on revision of project results and methodological aspects (UNIPI, M46)

WP2 Systems design and synergies:

- D2.1 Manual of participative design method for mixed and agroforestry systems (WR, M44)
- D2.2 Catalogue and assessment of designs for mixed and Agroforestry systems (EVILVO, M48)
- D2.3 Catalogue of European mixed and agroforestry initiatives and documentation of the two network meetings (ZHAW, M44)
- D2.4 Experiences from the first round of RID Pilots (EVILVO, M25)

WP3 Biophysical indicators and scenarios

- D3.1 Climate resilience: from concept to practice (AGROSCOPE, M36)
- D3.2 Climate resilience of mixed and agroforestry farming in Europe (CRAN, M36)
- D3.3 European target regions for Mixed Farming and Agroforestry (MVarc, M42)
- D3.4 Handbook of indicators with EIP-style factsheets for evaluating climate-smart farming systems and inventory guidelines (AFBI, M48)
- D3.5 Draft framework to identify European target regions for Mixed Farming and Agroforestry (MVarc, M30)
- D3.6 Climate resilience concept farming (AGRSOCOPE, M15)
- D3.7 Methodological approaches to access climate resilience (CRAN, M16)

WP4 Participatory research and tools for climate-smart transition

- D4.1 Multi-criteria assessment report of the 12 co-design pilots (ACTA, M39)

- D4.2 Participatory land plan for climate-smart MF and AF systems of the 6 codesign pilots (SSSA, M46)
- D4.3 MIX-App Prototype version (WR, M36)
- D4.4 MIX-App prototype participatory testing and evaluation report (WERVEL, M46)

WP5 Socio-economic, value chain and network assessment

- D5.1 Assessment of the farm level financial and socioeconomic performance of selected MF/AF systems (UNIFI, M12)
- D5.2 Characteristics of successful VCN (ORC, M12)
- D5.3 Acceptance, institutional barriers and conditions to adoption of successful and improved VCN approaches (UNIFI, M24)
- D5.4 Integrated economic and life cycle assessment of the impact of policy instruments to support improved mixed and forestry-based systems (ZALF, M32)
- D5.5 Guidelines for successful MFS value networks (CRAN, M36)

WP6 Policy co-development

- D6.1 Inventory report of current MF/AF policy instruments (AEEU, M12)
- D6.2 Policy scenarios in the EU, Eastern EU member states and four national states (CU, M24)
- D6.3 Report from 14 multistakeholder policy workshops for the codesign of MF/AF policies (CEEweb, M36)
- D6.4 EU-level MF/AF policy white paper and 'AGROMIX summit' (AEEU, M48)

WP7 Communication, dissemination and exploitation

- D7.1 Visual identity for the project, project website and communication tools (REV, M6)
- D7.2 Communication Plan and tools (REV, M12)
- D7.3 Report on Synergies in resilience research (CU, M24)
- D7.4 Report on the Knowledge Exchange Hubs (REV, M36)
- D7.5 Report on demonstrating effective communication engagement with stakeholders and media dissemination and exploitation (REV, M48)
- D7.6 Practice abstracts - batch 1 (REV, M12)
- D7.7 Practice abstracts - batch 2 (REV, M24)
- D7.8 Practice abstracts - batch 3 (REV, M36)

WP8 Coordination

- D8.1 Data Management Plan (CU, M6)

- D8.2 Documentation report of advisory board (CU, M46)
- D8.3 Quality assurance report (CU, M48)

6.3.5 Newsroom

This page will collect all news related to the project. An explanatory text opens the section page: *“Discover the work of the AGROMIX project, network and partners. It is very much a collaborative effort gathering contributions from partner organisations in an effort to highlight newsworthy information, activities, and stories”*. At present, the page has two posted articles: an article about the project published by REVOLVE magazine, and the press release from the AGROMIX kick off Meeting (Figure 18). In addition, a form has been added inviting users to share relevant news and material (Figure 19).

Newsroom

Discover the work of the AGROMIX project, network and partners. It is very much a collaborative effort gathering contributions from partner organisations in an effort to highlight newsworthy information, activities, and stories.

| All Publications

Figure 18: News page

Send us your news!

Do you have any articles, events, videos or images to share with the AGROMIX community?

Name

Email

Type:
 News Events Images Other

Upload files in pdf, doc, jpg or png format (max 2MB)

Your message (Remember to include the link to your event!)

Would you like to receive future updates from AGROMIX?
 Yes No

I accept the [privacy policy](#).

Figure 19: Content submission form

6.3.6 Events

<https://agromixproject.eu/events/>

This section will include information about the events where AGROMIX project and/or its results will be presented. The information will be categorised by type of event: webinar, workshop, conference, field day, open days, etc. The text introducing this section is: *“AGROMIX participates in events that provide a platform to share evidence-based research and demonstrate the benefits of mixed farming and agroforestry, while engaging with a variety of stakeholders”*. At present, the page announces two events: the May 2021 EURAF conference, and the Landscapes conference in September 2021 (Figure 20). The accompanying text that appears is the following:

EURAF 2021. Agroforestry for the transition towards sustainability and bioeconomy

The 5th European Agroforestry Conference will take place online. This event is hosted by EURAF (the European Agroforestry Federation) and provides an opportunity to present AGROMIX to the agroforestry research community, as well as to discuss emerging areas of research and land management. Read more: <https://www.euraf2020.eu/>

Landscape 2021. Diversity for Sustainable and Resilient Agriculture.

Landscape 2021 will take place online from 20-22 September 2021. Together with MIXED - one of our ‘sister’ projects - AGROMIX will present the project’s activities and objectives, and establish networks and synergies with complementary projects. Discover more about the conference: <https://www.landscape2021.org/frontend/index.php>

Events

AGROMIX participates in events that provide a platform to share evidence-based research and demonstrate the benefits of agroforestry and mixed farming, while engaging with a variety of stakeholders.

Upcoming Events

Figure 20: Events